

Stoichiometry and Kinetics of Oxidation of Hydrazine with Peroxymonophosphoric Acid in Acid Perchlorate Solutions in Presence of Trace Amounts of Iron(II)/Iron(III) and EDTA

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The title reaction has definite stoichiometry (i) and reproducible results only in the presence of edta and Fe^{II} or Fe^{III}.

An active form of H₂PO₄ appears to control the rate. The rate law (ii) holds

$$-d[\text{PMPA}]/dt = \frac{k[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_d} \quad (\text{ii})$$

where, *k* and *K_d* are the first order rate constant for the formation of active H₂PO₄ and the acid dissociation constant of normal H₂PO₄, respectively. *k* and *K_d* were found to be 1.22 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ and 0.37 *M*, respectively at 25° and *I* = 1.0 *M*.

THE oxidation of hydrazine with peroxydiphosphate (PDP) was reported by Kapoor and Gupta¹, in which the bottleneck of the reaction was hydrolysis of PDP to peroxymonophosphoric acid (PMPA) which in turn was responsible for the oxidation in a fast step. Similar reports have been made about nitrite¹, arsenic(III)² and antimony(III)¹. We have recently carried out the oxidation of nitrite³ with peroxymonophosphate and the second order rate constant was found to be several times larger than the hydrolysis constant. It therefore seemed to us worthwhile to study the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of hydrazine with PMPA, particularly in view of the fact that the oxidation of hypophosphite⁴ with PMPA and the hydrolytic reaction of PDP have comparable rates.

Hydrazine is one of those inorganic compounds which have been subjected to extensive kinetics studies, and a lot of work has been done with regard to its oxidation products. There is an excellent review by Higginson⁵ and a book by Audrieth and Ogg⁶. Largely two sets of oxidation products, nitrogen and ammonia, and nitrogen alone have been reported, according to one- or four-electron changes, respectively. Traces of azide are also said to be formed. Another aspect of the hydrazine systems is non-reproducibility of the results in some cases. Hydrazine is likely to form complexes⁷ with metal ions which are inadvertently present in traces in the reagents and they are responsible for the non-reproducibility. The nature of such metal ions have remained undefined so far. However, the presence of trace metal ions in the reagents, is not the only source of non-reproducibility. It also depends on the nature of the oxidant, particularly if free radicals are formed from them. The present paper deals

with the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of hydrazine with peroxymonophosphate in acid perchlorate solutions.

Experimental

Solutions of peroxymonophosphoric acid were prepared each day whenever required for the hydrolysis of peroxydiphosphate in 0.5 *M* HClO₄ at 45° for about 1 h. It was standardised iodometrically. Solutions of lithium perchlorate were prepared by neutralising HClO₄ (E. Merck) with lithium carbonate (AnalaR) to pH 6.8. Solutions of hydrazine were prepared by dissolving hydrazine sulphate (AnalaR) in water, the required quantity of BDH and these were standardised by bromate method⁸ using methylene blue as indicator. All other chemicals were either of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) quality and were used as such. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water, the second distillation being from potassium tetraoxomanganate(VII). All glass vessels used were of Corning make.

Kinetic procedure: Solutions of PMPA in aqueous perchloric acid in one flask and mixtures of hydrazine, perchloric acid and other required chemicals in the other flask were separately temperature-equilibrated in a thermostat at the specified temperature. The reaction was initiated by adding the required quantity of PMPA to the other flask containing hydrazine and other constituents. Progress of the reaction was followed by the decrease of PMPA, which was estimated iodometrically in ice-cold water. Aliquots (5 ml) were withdrawn after intervals of 10 to 15 min and added to ice-

cold 10% KI solution (10 ml). Although further hydrolysis of PMPA to H_2O_2 did not occur under the specified conditions, ice-cold solutions were employed to avoid liberation of iodine from H_2O_2 , if formed. Lithium perchlorate was employed to adjust the ionic strength.

Reproducibility: The results, as expected, were not reproducible and hence, EDTA was added to complex the trace metal ions. The end-point of iodometric estimation considerably improved by employing EDTA, which otherwise was not sharp. However, even after this, the results were not reproducible. The results were reproducible in the presence of Fe^{II} or Fe^{III} . The ranges of concentration of edta and Fe^{II} employed without any other side effect were $(1 \times 10^{-7} - 1 \times 10^{-4})$ and $(1 \times 10^{-8} - 1 \times 10^{-4})$ M, respectively. All the reactions were carried out in the presence of 2×10^{-5} M EDTA and 1×10^{-6} M Fe^{II} .

Preliminary experiments indicated that the kinetics results were unaffected by the presence of bisulphate ions, phosphate ions and trace amounts of H_2O_2 . The data were treated for the initial rates by the plane mirror method⁹. Rate constants were calculated from this and the duplicate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 10\%$.

Results

Stoichiometry: Excess PMPA was determined iodometrically and excess hydrazine was determined by bromate method⁹. The results are given in Table 1. The stoichiometry ($[PMPA]/[N_2H_4]$) varied from 1.3 to 1.8 depending on the ratio of the reactants. This shows that the oxidation occurs by both the mechanisms, one-electron change and four-electron transfer. However, in the presence

of iron(II) or iron(III), the stoichiometry was defined and equal to 1.98 ± 0.08 (1 mol hydrazine requiring 2 mol PMPA), according to the equation,

No ammonia could be detected. Nitrogen was detected qualitatively. This further shows a molecule of hydrazine undergoes four-electron change. By and large two or multi-electron oxidants, e.g. chromium(VI)¹⁰, iodine¹⁰, thallium(III)¹², H_2O_2 ¹³, $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ¹⁴, PDP¹, Np(VI)¹⁵, Pt(IV)¹⁶ etc. act as four-electron oxidants to oxidise hydrazine to nitrogen. On the other hand, one-electron oxidants, like cobalt(III)¹⁷, manganese(III)¹⁸, cerium(IV)¹⁹ and iron(III)²⁰ oxidise hydrazine to ammonia and nitrogen. However, in case of one-electron oxidants, things are not so simple and the stoichiometry depends also on the ratio of the reactants and the concentration of the acid. In the oxidation with cerium(IV)²¹, the stoichiometry ($[Ce^{IV}]/[N_2H_4]$) is 4 : 1 in high $[H_2SO_4]$ and 1 : 1 at high $([N_2H_4]/[Ce^{IV}]$) initial ratio. The facts of reproducibility of the results and the definite stoichiometry in the presence of iron(II)/iron(III), indicate that iron(II) gives a definite direction to the mechanism of reaction.

Variation of PMPA and hydrazine: The concentration of PMPA was varied in the range $(0.8-8.35) \times 10^{-3}$ M at fixed concentration of other reactants at two temperatures. A plot of initial rate vs $[PMPA]$ yields a straight line with a slope of 3.2×10^{-4} and $4.9 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ at 25 and 35°, respectively. The concentration of hydrazine was varied in the range $(0.4-20) \times 10^{-3}$ M and the rate was independent of its concentration. All these results are given in Table 2.

Hydrogen-ion dependence: The hydrogen-ion concentration was varied in the range 0.1-1.0 M with the help of $HClO_4$ at $I=1.0$ M adjusted with $LiClO_4$. The rate increases with the increase of $[H^+]$ and attains a limiting value at about and larger concentrations of 0.5 M $HClO_4$. The results at 25, 35 and 45° are given in Table 3.

Effect of iron(II), iron(III) and $(Fe^{III}-edta)$ complex: A few reactions were carried out in the presence of different concentrations of iron(II) and iron(III) and the edta complex of iron(III). The complex was prepared by mixing equivalent amounts of iron(III) and edta. The results given in Table 4, show that the rate is independent of the concentration of any of these reagents.

Reaction with phenylhydrazine and p-methylphenylhydrazine: Since the reaction of PMPA and hydrazine is independent of the concentration of hydrazine, reactions were also studied with phenylhydrazine and p-methylphenyl hydrazine. With $[PMPA]=4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M, $[H^+]=0.1$ M, $[EDTA]=2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ M, $[Fe^{III}]=1.0 \times 10^{-6}$ M, $[hydrazines]=0.001$ M, and at 45° and $I=0.5$ M, the initial rates ($M s^{-1}$) were found to be 2.9×10^{-6} , 2.7×10^{-6} and 2.8×10^{-6} for hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and p-methylphenylhydrazine, respectively. Thus it is

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY OF REACTION BETWEEN PEROXYMONOPHOSPHORIC ACID AND HYDRAZINE IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID SOLUTION IN PRESENCE OF Fe^{II}

$[HClO_4]=0.5$ M, $[Fe^{II}]=1 \times 10^{-6}$ M, Temp.=25°

$[PMPA] \times 10^3$ M	$[N_2H_4] \times 10^3$ M	$[PMPA]_{reacted}/[N_2H_4]_{reacted}$
2.44	1.00	1.86
3.25	1.00	1.87
4.88	1.00	1.90
6.50	1.00	1.95
8.12	4.00	2.02
8.12	6.00	1.89
1.59	4.00	1.94
1.59	10.00	1.98
2.00	2.00	2.08
2.00	3.00	2.12
2.00	4.00	2.15
2.00	5.00	2.04
3.90	20.00	1.32*
7.80	10.00	1.67*
23.50	10.00	1.72*
27.50	5.00	1.74*
23.55	5.00	1.83*

* In the absence of Fe^{II} .

TABLE 2—FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_o, s^{-1}) AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF PMPA AND HYDRAZINE

[EDTA]= $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Fe^{II}]= $1 \times 10^{-6} M$, [HClO₄]= $0.1 M$, I= $0.5 M$

25°				35°			
[PMPA] × 10 ³ M	[N ₂ H ₄ ⁺] × 10 ³ M	(ir) × 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹	k _o × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[PMPA] × 10 ³ M	[N ₂ H ₄ ⁺] × 10 ³ M	(ir) × 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹	k _o × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.66	1.0	0.56	3.4	0.80	1.0	0.37	4.6
2.49	1.0	0.82	3.3	1.60	1.0	0.80	5.0
4.15	1.0	1.25	3.0	2.40	1.0	1.18	4.9
4.98	1.0	1.55	3.1	3.30	1.0	1.69	5.1
6.64	1.0	2.32	3.5	4.10	1.0	2.00	4.9
7.47	1.0	2.54	3.4	4.95	1.0	2.50	5.0
8.15	1.0	2.83	3.5	5.80	1.0	2.88	5.0
2.50	0.4	0.75	3.0	6.65	1.0	3.37	5.1
2.50	0.6	0.68	2.8	8.35	1.0	4.33	5.2
2.50	1.0	0.68	2.8	3.40	1.0	1.60	4.7
2.50	2.0	0.85	3.4	3.40	2.0	1.60	4.7
2.50	3.0	0.73	2.9	3.40	4.0	1.60	4.7
2.50	4.0	0.80	3.2	3.40	5.0	1.70	5.0
2.50	5.0	0.86	3.4	3.40	8.0	1.70	5.0
2.50	6.0	0.74	3.0	3.40	9.0	1.65	4.9
2.50	7.0	0.86	3.4	3.40	10.0	1.70	5.0
2.50	8.0	0.86	3.4				
2.50	10.0	0.82	3.3				
2.50	20.0	0.84	3.4				
Average 3.2 ± 0.2				Average 4.9 ± 0.1			

TABLE 3—HYDROGEN-ION DEPENDENCE IN REACTION OF PMPA WITH HYDRAZINE

[PMPA]= $4.1 \times 10^{-3} M$, [N₂H₄⁺]= $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [EDTA]= $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Fe^{II}]= $1 \times 10^{-6} M$, I= $1.0 M$

[HClO ₄](M)	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.80	1.00
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹ (25°)	—	1.1	—	1.65	—	2.2	2.65	2.75	2.9	2.85	2.9
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹ (35°)	—	2.0	2.5	3.3	—	4.0	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.15	4.2
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹ (45°)	1.8	2.95	3.5	4.4	5.1	5.55	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.25	6.3

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} AND Fe^{III}-EDTA COMPLEX ON RATE OF REACTION BETWEEN PMPA AND HYDRAZINE

[PMPA]= $3.75 \times 10^{-3} M$, [N₂H₄⁺]= $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [EDTA]= $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, [H⁺]= $0.2 M$, I= $0.5 M$, Temp.=25°

[Fe ^{II}]/× 10 ⁴ M	0.01	0.1	1.0	10.0	100.0
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.1
[Fe ^{III}]/× 10 ⁴ M			1.0	10.0	100.0
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹			1.2	1.2	1.3
[Fe ^{III} -edta]/× 10 ⁴ M			1.0	10.0	100.0
(ir)/× 10 ⁶ M s ⁻¹			1.2	1.3	1.2

obvious that the rate is similar to that with hydrazine and the main rate determining step does not involve any of these hydrazines.

Effect of ionic strength: The ionic strength was varied from 0.5 to 2.5 M with lithium perchlorate at fixed concentrations of other reactants. The rate increases only slightly with the increase of ionic strength.

Discussion

Hydrazine would predominantly be present as N₂H₄⁺ in acid perchlorate medium since its protonation constant²² is large. Peroxymonophosphoric acid would be present as H₃PO₄ and H₂PO₄⁻ since its first acid dissociation constant²³ is 0.08 at 25°.

HPO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ species are not likely to be present in the acid solutions employed in the investigation. Since the rate increases with the increase of [H⁺] and becomes limiting at 0.5 M HClO₄, H₃PO₄ appears to be the reactive species.

Before giving any mechanism of the reaction, the following four facts have to be fully considered: (i) The rate has first order dependence on PMPA, (ii) the rate is independent of the concentration of N₂H₄⁺, (iii) the results are reproducible in the presence of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} and EDTA and (iv) the stoichiometry becomes definite in the presence of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III}. There could be three situations under which the rate can be independent of the concentration of hydrazine. (a) The reaction occurs by a chain mechanism in which chain initiating reaction might be the fission of H₃PO₄ molecule into a radical, just as peroxydisulphate yields a sulphate radical ion. (b) Hydrazine forms a complex with some metal ion and it is this complex (present in traces only) which acts as the reducing substance. (c) Some intermediate is obtained from PMPA in a rate determining step and the oxidation of hydrazine occurs in a fast step. So far there is no evidence for any type of radical from H₃PO₄ in thermal reactions. There is no evidence even in the case of H₄P₂O₈ or P₂O₈⁴⁻. There seems to be only a remote possibility for such a mechanism.

Since the rate is independent of the concentration of hydrazine it must involve in fast steps in the present system. Though Fe^{II} or Fe^{III} is not a reactant, the reaction appears to behave in its presence and hence, there should be some mechanistic role of Fe^{II} or Fe^{III} . The latter in traces is well known to act as a catalyst, but it is certainly not a catalyst in the present case. This is not unusual and is found in the oxidation²⁴ of hexacyanoferrate(II) with peroxodiphosphate in the presence of Fe^{III} and edta. From this it appears that the main reaction is essentially a chain reaction in which iron(II) terminates these chains which are responsible for irreproducibility. Since this happens in the fast steps, iron gives a direction to the reaction but does not appear in the rate law. That iron(II) or iron(III) does not actually participate in the redox process is proved by the fact that the stoichiometry ($[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_5]/[\text{N}_2\text{H}_4]$) is not 1 : 2.

It was found that PMPA alone does not initiate polymerisation of methyl methacrylate, but a mixture of PMPA and hydrazine does. The addition of $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ to the mixture of PMPA and hydrazine tremendously hastens the process of polymerisation. A mixture of PMPA and Fe^{II} also does not initiate polymerisation. This indirectly shows that the desired free radicals are produced only in the presence of iron(II) or iron(III).

The alternative (b) mentioned above does not seem probable since it would require rate dependence on iron(II). With respect to the third alternative, PMPA is likely to be present in two forms, normal and active, as in the case²⁵ of H_3PO_5 and H_3PO_5^* . Since the active form, which is five-coordinated, is more facile for the formation of transition state, this mechanism appears to be probable. In that case, the rate determining step would be the formation of the active form and the oxidation of hydrazine would occur in a fast step. Since the same rate is obtained for the oxidations of hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and *p*-methylphenylhydrazine, this mechanism appears to be probable.

The above mechanism would lead to the following rate law,

$$-d[\text{PMPA}]/dt = \frac{k[\text{PMPA}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_a} \quad (4)$$

From this, a plot of $(ir)^{-1}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ would yield a straight line with intercept (Fig. 1). This led to the values of k (s^{-1}) and K_a (M) to be 1.22×10^{-8} and 0.37 , 1.63×10^{-8} and 0.24 , and 2.2×10^{-8} and 0.20 at 25 , 35 and 45° , respectively. K_a values have the same order of magnitude as reported earlier (0.09 at 25° and $I=0.1 M$). The values reported in this work are at $I=1.0 M$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $(ir)^{-1}$ vs $[\text{HClO}_4]^{-1}$ at different temperatures; $[\text{PMPA}] = 4.1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{EDTA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, $I = 1.0 M$.

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